

KMU'S Development of Knowledge, Skills, and Professional Identity in Aesthetic Medicine

¹: Dr. Ammad Ali

MBBS, D-DERM, Certificate in Aesthetic Medicine KMU

²: Dr. Tabinda Ashfaq

MBBS FCPS (M.MED) Consultant aga Khan Karachi, HOD Isra University Karachi Campus, Certificate in Aesthetic Medicine KMU

³: Dr. Saad Ali

MBBS FCPS-II Training Medicine Registrar CMH Nowshera

⁴: Dr. Irsa Hidayat

MBBS FCPS-II Training Clinical Hematology BMTC CMH Rawalpindi

⁵: Dr. Kashif Ali

Aesthetic Medicine Specialist, Dermatologist, Cosmetologist

MBBS DRCOG MRCGP MSC D DERM DFSRH MBCAM MCFP

⁶: Dr. Laila Hassan

MBBS Aesthetic Medicine KMU

⁷: Dr. Zarka Sarwar

MBBS M-Phill AP Physiology DEPTT BKMC-MMC/MTI, Certificate in Aesthetic Medicine KMU

⁸: Dr. Muhammad Danyal Khan

MBBS , Dypty Medical Officer CMH PESH

Corresponding Author

Name: Dr. Tabinda Ashfaq

Designation: MBBS FCPS (M.MED) Consultant AGA Khan Karachi, HOD Isra University Karachi Campus, Aesthetic Medicine Diploma KMU

Abstract:- The current study looks into the inclusion of aesthetic medicine courses across Pakistan's public universities. This study sheds insight on the evolving landscape of aesthetic medicine education in the nation by examining the presence and commencement dates of the educational programmes. The findings of a survey conducted at various public universities show differing degrees of development in the introduction of the aesthetic medicine curriculum. Standardizing and putting into secure, research-based practice standards is crucial during the construction of a new medical spa. Patient safety must now more than ever be a major focus for providers as medical spas and beauty therapies spread and gain popularity. A structured medical model that is incorporated into the aesthetic consultation and treatment makes sure that the patient and the provider are involved in the decision-making process. The patient and the physician can decide whether the treatment will enhance the patient's general health and well-being together. The patient is given chance to completely comprehend all of the procedures available to them and to select the one that was best address heir over all psychological well-being, aesthetic concern ,and anatomical diagnostic. The physician might first weight the risks and rewards before deciding which intervention or treatment will benefit the patient most after coming to an understanding with them on a shared

objective. Patients are empowered in the decision making process when clinician's design and follow an intuitive decision making algorithm. By fostering a cooperative, trustworthy relationship between the patient and the physician, more satisfied and devoted patients can be attained. By aiding in the development of a standardized evaluation procedure in a medically based aesthetic practice, sharing this medical model algorithm with other aesthetic practitioners would be of tremendous assistance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The popularity of minimally invasive facial cosmetic procedures is rising globally. Injections of botulinum toxin or soft tissue fillers, chemical peels, and other minimally invasive procedures accounted for nearly 90% of the 15.6 million cosmetic procedures performed by plastic surgeons in 2020. In the United States alone, an estimated \$16.7 billion was spent on aesthetic procedures in 2020¹⁻³. Patient's opinions and comments are now more crucial than ever in establishing the efficacy of aesthetic treatments as aesthetic medicine continues to gain popularity. Technology advancements and the extensive use of social media have raised knowledge of many aesthetic standards and therapeutic objectives. There isn't much information comparing and contrasting the views of doctor and patient on facial aesthetic issues that needs to be prioritized for

treatment. by 2028, it is anticipated that the global medical aesthetic market would be worth close to \$125 billion⁴. According to a 2019 poll of 3465 customers by the American society of dermatologic surgery, around 70% of respondents were thinking about getting a cosmetic operation to boost their confidence and look younger or more appealing⁵. people are drawn to aesthetic clinic by the desire to depict a young, attractive face and body, which is accelerating the global rise of non-surgical aesthetic procedures. Reported by international aesthetic plastic surgeon's that procedures increased by 5.7% in 2020⁶. To improve patient outcomes, it is critical to identify and solve the training and knowledge gaps⁷. The authors of this paper propose other academic institutes to develop clinical training course just like Khyber medical university to educate future doctors in order to achieve safe and ideal clinical outcomes⁸⁻⁹.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted to review cross survey in education for aesthetic medicine in order to develop knowledge, skills, and a professional identity in public university of Pakistan. Khyber medical university is the only public sector providing this opportunity to doctors. The University of Lahore stands out as a pioneer among the universities examined because it has already incorporated aesthetic medicine into its programme and launched it on June 10, 2022. Following soon behind, Khyber Medical University successfully launched the programme on August 30, 2022. Even though they have been appraised, the Universities of Karachi, Peshawar, Baluchistan, Swat, Mardan (Awkum), University of Hazara, University of Dikhan, and King Edward University have not yet started their journeys in this particular subject.

III. RESULTS

Different public universities of Pakistan were analyzed for the education program in aesthetic medicine course in Pakistan.

Table 1 Different public universities of Pakistan were analyzed for the education program in aesthetic medicine course in Pakistan.

Public universities	Aesthetic medicine	Inauguration of program
university of Lahore	Present	10 June 2022
Khyber medical university	Present	30 AUG 2022
University of Karachi	N/A	N/A
University of Peshawar	N/A	N/A
University of Baluchistan	N/A	N/A
University of swat	N/A	N/A
University of mardan Awkum	N/A	N/A
University of hazara	N/A	N/A
University of dikhan	N/A	N/A
King Edward university	N/A	N/A

IV. DISCUSSION

The importance of this study rests in its recording of Pakistan's public universities' changing aesthetic medicine training environments. With the advent of aesthetic medicine courses, medical professionals may get specialized knowledge and abilities that will help them shape their professional identities to meet the demands of the modern medical landscape. The results of this study are anticipated to inform debates about developing curricula and lay the groundwork for future research and policy development in the area of aesthetic medicine education in Pakistan. This was Pakistan public based government universities survey. Aesthetic Physicians & dr kashif aesthetic use vocabulary to define ideals of facial aesthetic that was generally similar, describing female facial beauty used adjectives like beautiful, smooth and soft, while used the word handsome to describe male facial attractiveness. Next to neurotoxic and dermal filler injections, therapies aimed at improving skin quality were among the most popular minimally invasive procedures in 2020¹⁰. Every spot is important in aesthetic medicine but few studies shows that majority of aesthetics have periorbital areas as concern¹¹⁻¹² suggesting this area as particularly concern for beauty and attractiveness for women. Male concern are related to receding hairline & pattern baldness, now a days their concern are more to other modalities like platelets-rich plasma therapies, micro needling, topical etc. in improving hair growth than to hair transplants¹³⁻¹⁴. Gender and generational differences are always present in concerns to aesthetics. University of Lahore started this program on June 10-2022 on public level¹⁵ just hand on practice, Similarly Khyber medical university also started aesthetic medicine on 30 Aug 2022¹⁶, first university to provide diploma as well as planning for M.Sc. aesthetic medicine program that provides area of educational focus, help focus patient consults, and provides greater platform of learning. Aesthetic medicine is considered as specialty from Pakistan Medical Commission and Hec Pakistan. The analysis of aesthetic medicine education programmes at several public universities in Pakistan offers insightful information about the current situation of this specialized discipline within the nation's higher education system. According to the findings, there is a wide range in the programme availability and inauguration dates. The University of Lahore and Khyber Medical University has taken the initiative to include aesthetic medicine courses to their curricula among the universities evaluated. This proactive approach shows that the demand for cosmetic medical operations is increasing, and that medical personnel must be given the skills and information they need to effectively address this demand. However, a number of universities, including the Universities of Karachi, Peshawar, Baluchistan, Swat, Mardan (Awkum), University of Hazara, University of Dikhan, and King Edward University, have yet to include courses in aesthetic medicine in their curricula. This delay in implementation may be caused by a number of things, such as a lack of resources, difficulties developing the curriculum, and shifting priorities within these institutions.

V. CONCLUSION

As a result, the study of aesthetic medicine education programmes at several public universities in Pakistan demonstrates how varied and dynamic medical education is there. While some universities have already included pertinent courses and proactively accepted the value of aesthetic medicine education, other institutions have not yet incorporated this specialized topic into their curricula. In order to promote the growth and integration of aesthetic medicine education within medical programmes, the findings highlight the necessity of ongoing collaboration between academia, medical professionals, and policymakers. This advancement is necessary to give medical practitioners the information, abilities, and ethical considerations needed to deliver cosmetic treatments in a safe and effective manner. This development of postgraduate program was facilitated by Khyber medical university, which demonstrates a considerable advancement in education, which is essential to meet the rising need for licensed aesthetic physicians. This educational program will give graduates important insight into how their professional identities develop and how they are for independent clinical practice. Universities that have not yet started aesthetic medicine programmes in the future should think about the shifting dynamics of the healthcare industry and the possible advantages of providing specialized programmes to address patients' and society's changing requirements. It is crucial for medical education institutions to adapt and provide their students with a thorough understanding of this specialized specialty as the field of aesthetic medicine continues to grow in popularity.

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